

The Effect of E-Service Quality on E-Loyalty With E-Satisfaction as an Intervening for GoFood Application Users

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Abstract

The progress of technology and the circumstances surrounding the pandemic that requires restrictions on activities outside the home are used by the community to buy necessities through various ways, one of which is by using an online food delivery application. Application service quality is a factor that customers consider in using an online food ordering application. By focusing on the quality of application services, you can ensure user pleasure and develop a sense of loyalty among users. As an intermediary variable, this study aims to gather information on how quality attributes of e-services affect e-loyalty among GoFood users. E-Service Quality, E-Satisfaction, and E-Loyalty will help GoFood management better comprehend the impact on customers. Analyses of descriptive and causal data are conducted in this quantitative study. The population for this study was drawn from the Google Play Store's projected 50,000,000 downloads of the Gojek program. The Slovin formula was used to determine respondents, and 400 respondents were located in Indonesia via the GoFood program. With the criteria that respondents purchased food products in Indonesia using the GoFood app, we employed the purposive sampling technique to gather our data. Descriptive statistics and the Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis in the SmartPLS program were used to investigate the datasets. The findings of this study reveal that respondents responded to all research variables at a rate of 68 percent, which is considered acceptable. When efficiency, fulfillment, system availability, privacy, contact, and responsiveness hypotheses are examined, it shows a significant positive impact on e-satisfaction. E-satisfaction is unaffected by compensation at this time. The study's findings are expected to serve as an assessment for GoFood companies, especially in terms of fulfillment dimensions related to requirements and types of compensation that can be given to users who experience problems using the application.

Keywords: *E-Service Quality, E-Satisfaction, E-Loyalty, GoFood.*

INTRODUCTION

The benefits of convenience and speed offered in the use of technology are the right choice for people to save time and effort. The many choices and types of digital application services to facilitate the process of buying food also make consumers free to choose a service by comparing various factors.

According to research results from the Demographic Institute of the Faculty of Business Economics, University of Indonesia quoted from the Katadata website, from a survey conducted on 4,199 Gojek application users in 2020, the highest type of routine expenditure during the Covid-19 pandemic was used to buy food through online delivery services, namely 97% of respondents are e-service quality (Kata Data, 2020).

Gojek is a company in the field of online transportation services in Indonesia which was founded by Nadiem Makarim in 2010 under the management of PT. Application of the Nation's Children's Work. In the first year of its existence, Gojek was intended as a two-wheeled transportation that could be ordered through a call center service that became a liaison between drivers and customers. In 2015 Gojek received funding assistance with an investment system from investors and began launching Android and IOS-based applications to facilitate ordering its services, in the same year, Gojek began offering a variety of additional services, including food delivery and ticket sales. Gojek is Indonesia's first unicorn company, with a 3,600% increase in just 18 months. (Gojek, 2021).

GoFood is one of the service expansions from Gojek which was carried out in 2015. In its business process, GoFood cooperates with food SMEs and food restaurants, commonly referred to as GoFood partners. Currently, GoFood is the most useful and user-friendly application in the world during the pandemic. Thanks to Gojek's digitalization solution for MSMEs, food business partners at GoFood experienced 94% growth. MSME partners felt helped during the pandemic (Kirana, 2021).

User complaints regarding the GoFood delivery service application occur every year. According to information written on the Katadata online news page, in June 2019 various services in the Gojek application, one of which was GoFood, were

difficult for users to access. Users complain that the vouchers listed on GoFood cannot be claimed and used (Annur, 2019). Obstacles related to GoFood occurred again in 2020. On the Kompas 11 daily website released in October 2020, it was reported that news related to various services on the Gojek application were difficult to access (Clinton, 2020). In 2021, the GoFood application is also reported to have experienced various obstacles. As reported by KumparanTech on its website page, Gofood users must be disappointed because the GoFood service cannot be used. The GoFood service obstacle occurs when the user wants to process the order check up to payment (Ludwianto, 2021). Complaints related to GoFood were also conveyed by users through Gojek application reviews on Playstore. These complaints, if left unchecked and not immediately resolved, will have an impact on the dissatisfaction of GoFood users which can then cause GoFood users to switch to other online food delivery applications due to problems and complaints that keep happening.

LITERATURE REVIEW

E-Service Quality

It is the ability of an e-commerce site to expedite the purchase process and deliver goods purchased by customers that is referred to as E-service quality. As stated by Santoso (Suwondo et al., 2017), e-service quality refers to the complete quality of service delivery to clients in the marketplace or via virtual company activities. The E-S-QUAL and E-RecS-QUAL were created by Parasuraman and his colleagues. E-S-QUAL services are evaluated in the first step for their efficacy and fulfilment, as well as for their system accessibility and privacy. E-RecS-second QUAL's troubleshooting method asks consumers to analyze three different areas of their system: responsiveness, compensation, and engagement.

1. Efficiency is the benefit that consumers can receive from being able to easily use and access or perform searches in accessing product information.
2. Fulfillment is the accuracy or accuracy of application or website service promises regarding transactions carried out in accordance with the time and goods available as promised to the user.
3. System Availability is the ability of service providers to provide functions that run smoothly and correctly on application pages or websites.
4. Privacy is the ability of service providers to provide application security to protect customer data from fraud and leakage of personal information.
5. Responsiveness is the ability of service providers to provide quick responses when dealing with application usage problems or questions about applications or websites.
6. Compensation is the ability of service providers to provide compensation in the form of refunds for shipping fees and service fees when problems occur in using the application or website.
7. Contact is the service provider's ability to provide assistance via online services or phone calls when problems occur while using an application or website.

E-Satisfaction

Service quality is an important element of customer perception. In services combined with physical products such as IT services, customers' satisfaction with in-person or automated services is strongly influenced by the quality of the service provided. When it comes to digital business, customer satisfaction is called e-satisfaction. According to Oliver in Della Prisanti et al. (2017) e-satisfaction is the result of consumer evaluation of emotions questioning whether or not the application's online shopping experience meets the expectations of consumers. Customers' electronic contentment is the sum total of their overall pleasure with their online experience purchases and experiences with a company's products or services (Kim et al. in Sasono et al., 2021).

Each definition will result in a different understanding for each type of business such as in business organizations, or online groups, including government, educational, nonprofit, and political websites. This demonstrates the need to develop e-satisfaction measures that can be used across all disciplines and assess the effectiveness of websites for all types of businesses. From some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that e-satisfaction is the satisfaction felt by customers with products or services that can be received and felt from ordering or purchasing products or services online.

E-Loyalty

An online business venture that is successful and failed, can be seen from the repeated purchases of its loyal customers. According to Anderson in Al-dweeri et al. (2017), e-loyalty has parallels with the concept of loyalty to an establishment owned by customers. Loyalty results in purchase behavior and returns to the product or service provider. Being the first choice, giving positive comments regarding products, recommending others to access the website is an illustration of customer loyalty in shopping online. (Yang and Tsai in Ting et al. (2016). E-loyalty refers to actions to be able to generate

and maintain customer loyalty in a virtual business. The dimensions and indicators of measuring the e-loyalty variable in this study refer to aspects of e-loyalty measurement loyalty described in the research of Rashwan et al. (2019).

Researchers found that e-satisfaction and e-relationship are influenced by seven characteristics of e-service quality that include efficiency and fulfillment as well as privacy and responsiveness (2021). Here, the theoretical framework is depicted in the form of Figure 1.

Figure 1. Thinking Framework

The following hypotheses are based on the context, past research, and the study approach outlined above:

1. Efficiency has a positive and significant effect on E-Satisfaction on GoFood users
2. Fulfillment has a positive and significant effect on E-Satisfaction on GoFood users
3. System availability has a positive and significant effect on E-Satisfaction on GoFood users
4. Privacy has a positive and significant effect on E-Satisfaction on GoFood users
5. Contact has a positive and significant effect on E-Satisfaction on GoFood users
6. Responsiveness has a positive and significant effect on E-Satisfaction on GoFood users
7. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on E-Satisfaction on GoFood users
8. E-Service Quality has a significant effect on E-Satisfaction on GoFood users
9. E-Service Quality has a significant effect on E-Loyalty on GoFood users
10. E-Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on E-Loyalty on GoFood users
11. E-Satisfaction mediates the positive and significant effect of E-Service Quality on E-Loyalty on GoFood users.

METHOD

In this quantitative investigation, descriptive and causal data are analyzed. The estimated population was used in this investigation 50,000,000 downloads of the Gojek application from the Google Play Store. The sample approach utilized is non-probability sampling with an emphasis on purposive sampling. Determination of respondents using the Slovin formula so as to get 400 respondents using the GoFood application in Indonesia. The data collection technique is by distributing questionnaires through the help of the Google Form application. In the end, the data was analyzed using the SmartPLS tool for descriptive and SEM analysis.

The paradigm in this research is positivism. The approach used in theory development is a deductive approach. Based on the unit of analysis, this research was conducted on individuals or individuals who have used the online food ordering application in the GoFood application. In this study, the researcher did not participate actively and only occasionally interacted with the social group being studied. The research that was utilised has a natural history. This study is a cross-sectional one because of the implementation time.

In this study, content validity was carried out by examining questionnaire items from previous studies and then modifying the questionnaire items based on research needs. The author also conducted face validity with three experts in the field of marketing and after that a pilot test was carried out to 30 respondents. In this study, the Cronbach Alpha coefficient with a minimum value of 0.70 was used to conduct reliability testing. Furthermore, this study found that the results of the questionnaire pilot test's validity and reliability assessment were valid and reliable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of a Descriptive Analyses

Based on Table 1 the highest score from the descriptive analysis is efficiency with a score of 91.9% and the lowest is compensation with a score of 78.0%.

Table1. Descriptive Test Results

Variable	Total Score	Ideal Score	% Score
Efficiency	3676	4000	91.9%
Fulfillment	3451	4000	86.3%
System Availability	3541	4000	88.5%
Privacy	3345	4000	83.6%
Contact	3314	4000	82.9%
Responsiveness	3202	4000	80.1%
Compensation	3119	4000	78.0%
E-Satisfaction	10566	12000	88.1%
E-Loyalty	15812	20000	79.1%

Test Outer Model

Convergent validity test was conducted to test the level of accuracy of the items in measuring the object of research. For convergent validity, the loading factor criteria with a value of more than 0.7 and an AVE of more than 0.5 are used (Abdillah & Hartono, 2015). Table 2 shows that all of the survey items are valid, as seen in the findings below.

Table 2. Convergent Validity Test Results

Latent variable	Indicator	Loading factor (> 0.7)	T statistics	AVE (> 0.5)	Conclusion
Efficiency	EF1	.888	40.774	.818	Valid
	EF2	.921	76.440		Valid
Fulfillment	FU1	.921	110.510	.848	Valid
	FU2	.921	96.787		Valid
System availability	SA1	.948	201.711	.879	Valid
	SA2	.926	79.009		Valid
Privacy	PR1	.959	137.174	.921	Valid
	PR2	.960	115.101		Valid
Contact	CT1	.899	75.140	.792	Valid
	CT2	.881	45.118		Valid
Responsiveness	RE1	.895	43.913	.826	Valid
	RE2	.922	102.110		Valid
Compensation	CO1	.943	152.634	.902	Valid
	CO2	.956	229.024		Valid
E-Satisfaction	ES1	.864	43.282	.778	Valid
	ES2	.898	73.215		Valid
	ES3	.886	56.216		Valid
	ES4	.839	46.096		Valid
	ES5	.851	48.621		Valid
	ES6	.949	206.433		Valid
E-Loyalty	EL1	.781	31.778	.660	Valid
	EL2	.787	35.223		Valid
	EL3	.857	52.018		Valid
	EL4	.871	54.901		Valid
	EL5	.806	42.120		Valid
	EL6	.788	37.540		Valid
	EL7	.869	50.756		Valid
	EL8	.819	44.509		Valid
	EL9	.721	22.402		Valid
	EL10	.814	39.028		Valid

In order to determine whether or not the survey's questions are genuine, we utilize a metric called composite reliability. The recommended value for Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and excellent Rho A is larger than 0.7, according to Hair et al. in Abdillah & Hartono (2015). Table 3. below shows that all of the questionnaire items can be considered to be reliable.

Table 3. Composite Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	C.R.
Compensation	.891	.903	.948
Contact	.737	.740	.884
E-Loyalty	.943	.948	.951
E-Satisfaction	.942	.944	.954
Efficiency	.779	.794	.900
Fulfillment	.821	.821	.918
Privacy	.914	.914	.959
Responsiveness	.791	.802	.905
System availability	.863	.881	.935

Inner Model Test

In this study, the researcher used a 95% confidence level. According to Indrawati (2015), business research usually uses a 95% confidence level. For the one-tailed hypothesis, the route coefficient score indicated by the T-Statistic value must be above 1.64. (Abdillah & Hartono, 2015). Inferred from the data in Table 4, the results show that the hypothesis is accepted except for the compensation hypothesis.

Table 4. T-Statistics Test Results

Hypothesis	Connection	Path	T statistics	P-Value	Hypothesis Alternative
Direct					
1	<i>Efficiency -> E-Satisfaction</i>	.190	4.099	.000	Received
2	<i>Fulfillment -> E-Satisfaction</i>	.149	2.276	.023	Received
3	<i>System availability -> E-Satisfaction</i>	.187	2.642	.009	Received
4	<i>Privacy -> E-Satisfaction</i>	.111	2.443	.015	Received
5	<i>Contact -> E-Satisfaction</i>	.175	2.445	.015	Received
6	<i>Responsiveness -> E-Satisfaction</i>	.140	2.030	.043	Received
7	<i>Compensation -> E-Satisfaction</i>	.054	0.917	.360	Rejected
10	<i>E-Satisfaction -> E-Loyalty</i>	.670	20.555	.000	Received
Indirect					
11	<i>Efficiency -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Loyalty</i>	.127	4.020	.000	Received
	<i>Fulfillment -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Loyalty</i>	.100	2.262	.024	Received
	<i>System availability -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Loyalty</i>	.125	2.620	.009	Received
	<i>Privacy -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Loyalty</i>	.074	2.426	.015	Received
	<i>Contact -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Loyalty</i>	.117	2.428	.015	Received
	<i>Responsiveness -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Loyalty</i>	.094	2.020	.043	Received
	<i>Compensation -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Loyalty</i>	.036	0.916	.360	Rejected

The following test is a visual inspection of the R-Square. If the external latent variable changes, the R-Square has a substantive influence on the endogenous latent variable (Abdillah & Hartono, 2015). The R-Square number illustrates the dependent variable's influence. The following describes how to obtain the R-Square value.

Table 5. Results from the R Squared Test

	R-Square
E-Satisfaction	0.634
E-Loyalty	0.448

Customers' e-satisfaction is influenced by an R-Square (coefficient of determination) of 0.634, where efficiency, satisfaction, availability of the system and the capacity to access personal information are only some of the many considerations that are included. Efficiency has the highest impact on electronic satisfaction, with a path coefficient of 0.190; compensation has the lowest impact, with a path coefficient of 0.054. The R-Square score of 0.448 for the association between e-loyalty and the second substructure is 44.8 percent explained by the e-satisfaction variable.

Customer satisfaction and loyalty can be evaluated using F tests, or simultaneous testing, to see if e-service quality subvariables such as efficiency and fulfillment affect their feelings of happiness and loyalty. The F test is another name for simultaneous testing. A statistical test known as the F test is used to assess if all of the model's independent variables have a cumulative influence on the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2016). There is significance if $F_{count} > F_{table}$, but insignificance if $F_{count} < F_{table}$. H_0 is ruled out in the second-to-last scenario. Using a total sample size of 400 and a F_{table} of 2.03, the value of F_{count} is compared to the value of F_{count} in this study.

Table 6. Simultaneous E-Service Quality Hypothesis Calculation of E-Loyalty

Variable		F-Count	F-Table	Description	
<i>E-Service Quality</i>	→	<i>E-Satisfaction</i>	97,01	2,03	Significant

Based on the calculation results, the F_{count} value is 97.01. Value H_0 is rejected if $F_{count} > F_{table}$. According to study, e-service quality and e-satisfaction are strongly linked.

Table 7. Simultaneous E-Service Quality Hypothesis on E-Satisfaction Calculation

Variable		F-Count	F-Table	Description	
<i>E-Service Quality</i>	→	<i>E-Loyalty</i>	45,45	2,03	Significant

Based on the calculation results, the F_{count} value is 45.45. Value If $F_{count} > F_{table}$ then H_0 is rejected, which indicates that e-loyalty and the quality of e-services are intimately linked.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This hypothesis has a positive path coefficient (0.190), a T-statistic of $4.099 > 1.64$, and a P-Value of $0.000 < 0.05$, according to the results of the test. Research H_1 may now be complete. e-satisfaction has a strong correlation with efficiency, which is consistent with the first hypothesis, but not with hypothesis zero (H_0). This helps to understand why using GoFood to order meals is so convenient. E-satisfaction rises as efficiency rises; conversely, as efficiency falls, customer e-satisfaction falls. In line with previous research by San et al. (2020), this study's findings show that customer satisfaction with online purchases in Malaysia is positively impacted by efficiency. Efficiency is a major factor in customer satisfaction when purchasing goods online through the Amazon.com website in Jordan, according to Al-dweeri et al (2017). It is essential for online business owners to practice efficiency in the advancement of business processes because efficiency is a crucial factor in determining customer satisfaction (Hasman et al., 2019). Due to the route coefficient (0.149), the T-Statistic ($2.276 > 1.64$), and the P-Value ($0.023 < 0.05$), the second hypothesis is discarded. Fulfillment has a significant impact on e-satisfaction, as shown by the second study's acceptance of H_1 while rejecting H_0 . For example, this demonstrates how the GoFood app can ensure that delivery requests are fulfilled and that items are available when promised to customers. Jenius BTPN app users in Indonesia are more satisfied with the app when they feel fulfilled, according to the findings of this study, which support Sidik & Indrawati's (2021) research. Fulfillment, according to Rita et al. (2019).s research, is one of the most important aspects of e-service quality in Indonesian online retail sites. In the online retail industry, fulfillment is a critical contact and procedure between sellers and consumers (Jain et al. 2017).

To test the third hypothesis, the path coefficient is positive (0.187), with a T-statistic of $2.642 > 1.64$ and a P-value of $0.009 < 0.05$. This means that the third hypothesis is correct. A favorable effect of system availability on e-satisfaction has been found, hence H_1 is approved whereas H_0 is refused. In light of this, the GoFood program's ease of use and effectiveness can be explained. The study's findings corroborate Pudjarti et al. (2019)'s finding that system availability has an effect on the satisfaction of Gojek and Grab application users in Semarang City. In research on online retailers in Malaysia (San et al., 2020), system availability is the strongest predictor of customer satisfaction among other levels of e-service quality predictors. System availability has a direct correlation with customer e-satisfaction; conversely, system availability has a direct correlation with customer e-satisfaction. The route coefficient is positive (0.111), when the fourth hypothesis is evaluated, the T-Statistic is $2.443 > 1.64$ and the P-Value is $0.015 < 0.05$. Privacy has a favorable impact on customer happiness, as shown by H_1 , but H_0 cannot be accepted. This explains that the GoFood application can protect customers from fraud and the leaking of personal information of customers who use it. Studying the Amazon.com website in Jordan, Al-dweeri and his colleagues (2017) found that privacy is a significant aspect that influences customer happiness. In the research of Al-Hawary & Al-Smeran (2017) which states that in dealing with online services, customer privacy security is an influential factor in creating online banking customer satisfaction in Jordan. Privacy has a great impact on the shopping experience and the level of quality of online business and can be an evaluation of e-commerce customer satisfaction (Radziszewska, 2018). Increased customer satisfaction can be achieved if privacy is better; a decrease in customer satisfaction can be achieved by a poor privacy level.

Furthermore, in testing the fifth hypothesis, In this case, the path coefficient is positive at 0.175. Both the T-Statistic and the P-Value results were $2.445 > 1.64$ and $0.015 < 0.05$. H_1 can be accepted and H_0 refused, which indicates that customers who shop online are more likely to report being satisfied if they are able to make touch with the merchant.

This explains that the GoFood application is felt to be able to provide assistance through online services when users experience problems when using the application. The existence of a menu and contact information for assistance that can be directly accessed online helps GoFood users in solving problems that occur when using the application. The findings of this study corroborate those of Ting et al. (2016), They found that customer happiness on Malaysian online purchasing platforms is influenced by the quality of e-service contact. It has also been found that the contact dimension has an important and positive impact on the e-satisfaction of BTPN Jenius app users in Indonesia (Sidik & Indrawati, 2021). An important factor contributing to the satisfaction of Indonesian online banking consumers is the availability of a human point of contact (Sasono et al., 2021). Better customer service is linked to higher levels of customer e-satisfaction, while poorer service is linked to lower levels of customer e-satisfaction. A T-Statistic of 2,030 > 1.64, with a P-Value of 0.043 < 0.05, indicates that the route coefficient is positive (0.140) for the sixth hypothesis. Findings support the hypothesis that responsiveness has a considerable impact on customer satisfaction with their e-commerce experience, while rejecting the hypothesis that responsiveness has no effect. When a user has a problem with the GoFood app, they can expect a speedy response. The study's findings corroborate research by Al-Hawary and Al-Smeran (2017) that responsiveness is a critical component in generating online banking customer happiness and that responsiveness is the strongest variable impacting consumer e-satisfaction (Ting et al., 2016). Researchers have found that responsiveness is linked to consumer happiness and loyalty in Indian e-commerce (Sundram et al., 2017). It is imperative for a company's success in today's technological world to respond quickly to customer complaints. Customer satisfaction is higher when responsiveness is high, whereas customer dissatisfaction is lower when responsiveness is low, according to data analysis results. Customers' opinions gathered through an online survey.

Furthermore, from the results of tests carried out on the seventh hypothesis, the path coefficient value is positive with a fairly low value compared to other variables, namely 0.054. When looking at the T-Statistic of 0.917 < 1.64 and the P-Value of 0.360 > 0.05, it's clear that this is the case. Because H1 of the seventh hypothesis research has been rejected, and H0 accepted, it can be inferred that compensation has no substantial effect on e-satisfaction. According to Sidik & Indrawati (2021), a study of BTPN Jenius app users found that compensation had no effect on e-satisfaction in a favorable or substantial way. Data study shows that consumers believe the GoFood app doesn't do enough to compensate them when they run into issues with the service. GoFood companies must improve the system of giving and claiming compensation if customers experience difficulties and losses caused by using the application. GoFood must be able to provide clear and directed information and services regarding compensation to users who experience difficulties or losses when using the application so that the compensation process goes well and can provide satisfaction for users. The following test is a concurrent test. Simultaneous testing revealed that Fcount of 97.01 was greater than Ftable of 2.03. H1 of this study is accepted, but H0 is rejected, demonstrating that e-satisfaction and e-service quality are linked. Increasing consumer happiness in Mongolian internet enterprises is based on the quality of service offered, according to a study by Chimed-ochir & Tumurbaatar (2019). E-commerce customer loyalty hinges greatly on customer happiness, according to a study on the subject of excellent e-service (Sundaram et al., 2017). Online banking customer satisfaction in Indonesia is primarily driven by aspects relating to the quality of e-services (Sasono et al., 2021). Customers who are more satisfied with an e-overall service's quality are more inclined to rate it highly as a result of data research. -the contentment of the customer.

Furthermore, the tests carried out on the ninth hypothesis showed that Fcount of 45.45 was greater than Ftable of 2.03. Because H1 of the ninth study has been approved, and H0 has been denied, it may be concluded that the quality of an e-service influences customer loyalty. According to the research of Sasono et al. (2021), internet banking users in Indonesia are more likely to remain loyal to their bank if they receive better e-service quality. It is the goal of Reicheld and Schefter in Ting et al., (2016), to ensure a mutually beneficial relationship between sellers and customers in online business through websites, according to Reicheld. Customer acquisition costs are much higher than customer retention costs, so building customer loyalty through e-loyalty is important from a marketing perspective. Quality of e-services depends on the loyalty of customers' impressions of the quality of the service they receive, according to Al-dweeri et al. (2017)'s research. To put it another way, consumers' e-loyalty declines, which in turn affects e-service quality, and this decrease is directly linked to a decrease in customer satisfaction. -Follow-up from loyal customers. After the tenth hypothesis was tested, the path coefficient was discovered to be positive (0.670), with a T-Statistic of 20,555 > 1.64 and a P-Value of 0.000 < 0.05. Consequently, H1 is accepted and rejected in the tenth investigation, which shows that e-satisfaction influences e-loyalty in a positive and significant manner. According to Alkhoul's (2017) research, Swedish online banking customers were found to have higher degrees of e-loyalty if they were satisfied with their service. Prior studies, such as the Taobao website (Ling, 2011) and a study of customers who buy from e-commerce in the United States, have found a strong link between e-satisfaction and customer loyalty, according to Kim EY in Ting et al. (2016). It's a (Kim and Jackson, 2011). This demonstrates that retaining customers over the long run has its advantages. E-service quality and satisfaction are linked to banking websites in a study conducted by Sasono, et al. (2021). Students' e-satisfaction with Indonesian online banking websites will enhance if the quality of electronic services is improved. It is possible for customers' perceptions of e-loyalty to be affected by the amount of their e-satisfaction and vice versa.

Results showed that e-satisfaction had a positive path coefficient and a T-statistic more than 1.64 and a P-Value less than 0.05 in the mediation hypothesis testing of the relationship between e-service quality factors like efficiency and fulfillment. The relationship between the e-service quality (compensation) subvariable and e-loyalty was not positively affected by the influence of e-satisfaction in mediation with compensation. Even though H1 was approved in this study, e-satisfaction appears to have an important role in moderating the association between service quality and customer loyalty. As stated by Sasono and colleagues in 2021, e-satisfaction influences customer satisfaction. Consumer satisfaction with the Jenius Bank BTPN application, according to Sidik and Indrawati, is linked to both high-quality e-services and long-term customer loyalty in Indonesia. e-satisfaction serves as an intermediary between service quality and client loyalty in Jordanian online shopping, according to Al-dweeri et al (2017). Research conducted in 2017 by Alkhouli verifies these three hypotheses on the effect of customer satisfaction with bank websites' e-service quality and e-loyalty. Online client satisfaction and loyalty can only be achieved through high-quality website services, according to a survey.

CONCLUSION

From the research results, compensation does not have a positive relationship with customer e-satisfaction, while in terms of efficiency, fulfillment, system availability, privacy, contact, responsiveness it has a positive relationship with e-satisfaction. E-loyalty and e-satisfaction are both affected by the overall quality of electronic services (efficiency, compliance, system availability, privacy, contact, responsiveness, rewards) (simultaneously). As a link between service quality and customer loyalty, e-satisfaction is proven to help in building customer loyalty.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdillah, W., & Hartono, J. (2015). *Partial Least Square (PLS) Alternatif Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Dalam Penelitian Bisnis*. ANDI.
- [2]. Al-dweeri, R. M., Obeidat, Z. M., Al-dwiry, M. A., Alshurideh, M. T., & Alhorani, A. M. (2017). The Impact of E-Service Quality and E-Loyalty on Online Shopping: Moderating Effect of E-Satisfaction and E-Trust. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 9(2), 92. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijms.v9n2p92>
- [3]. Al-Hawary, S. I. S., & Al-Smeran, W. F. (2017). Impact of Electronic Service Quality on Customers Satisfaction of Islamic Banks in Jordan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 7(1), 170–188. <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarafms/v7-i1/2613>
- [4]. Alkhouli, S. (2017). The Effect of Banks Website Service Quality and E-satisfaction on E-loyalty: An Empirical Study on Swedish Banks. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 13(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v13n1p1>
- [5]. Annur, C. M. (2019). *Pengguna Mengeluh Tak Bisa Akses Layanan, Ini Penjelasan Gojek*. <https://katadata.co.id/desyetyowati/digital/5e9a518361af4/aplikasi-alami-gangguan-teknis-ini-penjelasan-gojek>
- [6]. Chimed-ochir, D., & Tumurbaatar, C. (2019). Service Quality Effects On Purchase Intention And Customer Satisfaction: In Case Of E-Commerce Industry In Mongolia. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 2(03), 49–58. <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.35409/IJBMER.2019.4958>
- [7]. Clinton, B. (2020). *Layanan Gojek Alami Gangguan Malam Ini*. <https://tekno.kompas.com/read/2020/10/08/19251817/layanan-gojek-alami-gangguan-malam-ini>
- [8]. Della Prisanti, M., Suyadi, I., & Arifin, Z. (2017). Pengaruh E-Service Quality Dan E-Trus Terhadap E-Customer Satisfaction Serta Implikasinya Terhadap E-Customer Loyalty (Studi pada Nasabah PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kantor Cabang Pembantu Lawang). *Journal of Business Studies*, 19(1), 2443–3837.
- [9]. Ghozali, I. (2016). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IBM SPSS 23* (8th ed.). Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [10]. Gojek. (2021). *Milestone*. <https://www.gojek.com/id-id/about/>
- [11]. Hasman, H. C. P., Ginting, P., & Rini, E. S. (2019). The Influence of E-Service Quality on E-Satisfaction and Its Impact on Repurchase Intention in Using E- Commerce Applications on Students of Universitas Sumatera Utara. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 6(10), 299–307.
- [12]. Indrawati, P. D. (2015). *Metode Penelitian Manajemen Dan Bisnis (Konvergensi Teknologi Komunikasi Dan Informasi)*. Refika Aditama.
- [13]. Kata Data. (2020). *Pesan Makanan Online Jadi Pengeluaran Terbanyak Konsumen saat Pandemi*. <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2020/10/12/pesan-makanan-online-jadi-pengeluaran-terbanyak-konsumen-saat-pandemi>
- [14]. Kirana. (2021). *Bangkitkan UMKM di Tengah Pandemi bersama Gojek*. <https://feb.ugm.ac.id/id/berita/3195-bangkitkan-umkm-di-tengah-pandemi-bersama-gojek>
- [15]. Ludwianto, B. (2021). *Layanan GoFood Down, Pengguna Gojek Tak Bisa Pesan Makanan*.

<https://doi.org/https://kumparan.com/kumparantech/layanan-gofood-down-pengguna-gojek-tak-bisa-pesan-makanan-1vMKYOWPHDK/full>

- [16]. Pudjarti, S., Nurchayati, N., & Dwi Putranti, H. R. (2019). Penguatan Kepuasan Model Hubungan E-Service Quality Dan E-Loyalty Pada Konsumen Go-Jek Dan Grab. *Sosiohumaniora*, 21(3), 237–246. <https://doi.org/10.24198/sosiohumaniora.v21i3.21491>
- [17]. Radziszewska, A. (2018). Quality Assessment of E-Commerce Service in The Context of Customer Experiences. *MAPE*, 1(1), 635.
- [18]. Rashwan, H. H. M., M. Mansi, A. L., & Hassan, H. E. (2019). The impact of the E- CRM (expected security and convenience of website design) on E- loyalty field study on commercial banks. *Journal of Business & Retail Management Research*, 14(01), 106–122. <https://doi.org/10.24052/jbrmr/v14is01/art-10>
- [19]. Rita, P., Oliveira, T., & Farisa, A. (2019). The impact of e-service quality and customer satisfaction on customer behavior in online shopping. *Heliyon*, 5(10), e02690. <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.5539/ijms.v9n2p92>
- [20]. San, W. H., Yee, W., & Qureshi, M. I. (2020). Impact Of E-Service Quality On Customer Satisfaction In Malaysia. *Journal of Marketing and Information Systems*, 3(1). <http://readersinsight.net/JMIS>
- [21]. Sasono, I., Jubaedi, A. D., Novitasari, D., Wiyono, N., Riyanto, R., Oktabrianto, O., Jainuri, J., & Waruwu, H. (2021). The Impact of E-Service Quality and Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty: Empirical Evidence from Internet Banking Users in Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 465–473. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no4.0465>
- [22]. Sidik, M., & Indrawati. (2021). *Pengaruh E-Service Quality Terhadap Customer Loyalty dengan Customer Satisfaction Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pengguna Jenius BTPN*. Telkom.
- [23]. Sundaram, V., Ramkumar, D., & Shankar, P. (2017). Impact of E-Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty Empirical Study in India Online Business. *Kinerja*, 21(1), 48. <https://doi.org/10.24002/kinerja.v21i1.1034>
- [24]. Suwondo, A., Sarana, & Marjan, F. I. (2017). Analisis Pengaruh E-Kepuasan Pelanggan Terhadap E-Loyalitas Pelanggan Kai Access Berdasarkan E-Servqual Pada Pt Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) Daop Iv Semarang Program Studi Komputerisasi Akuntansi , Politeknik Negeri Semarang Pendahuluan Pada Era Globa. *Prosiding Sentrinov (Seminar Nasional Terapan Riset Inovatif)*, 3, 338–360. <http://proceeding.sentrinov.org/index.php/sentrinov/article/view/196>
- [25]. Ting, O. S., Ariff, M. S. M., Zakuan, N., Sulaiman, Z., & Saman, M. Z. M. (2016). E-Service Quality, E-Satisfaction and E-Loyalty of Online Shoppers in Business to Consumer Market; Evidence form Malaysia. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 131(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/131/1/012012>
- [26]. Zeithaml, V. A., Bitner, M. J., & Gremler, D. D. (2017). Services Marketing Integration Customer Focus Across the Firm. In *Business Horizons* (Seventh Ed, Vol. 51, Issue 3). McGraw-Hill Education. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2008.01.008>